

Layers of Unpredictability: Developing the Aesthetic and Identity of a Network-Based Live Coding Ensemble

Mynah Marie
Independent
Researcher
mynah@
earthtoabigail.com

Shelly Knotts
Independent
Researcher
shelly@
datamusician.net

Eldad Tsabary
Concordia
University
eldad.tsabary@
concordia.ca

Melandri Laubscher
University
of Pretoria
m.laubscher@
tuks.co.za

ABSTRACT

Live coding often involves a feedback loop between machine and human performers who understand the code both through the knowledge of the coding language and the embodied understanding of the output, i.e. the action of listening. The unpredictability of live coding is entangled with and heightened by the considerations behind a remote collective practice and the use of a collaborative interface designed to provide three main channels of communication to the collaborators: written characters, sound, and visuals.

The ability to navigate multiple layers of unpredictability, combined with a constant awareness of each performer's individual aesthetic and the accumulation of individual and group experiences are the foundations for an ensemble to develop a group identity. In this paper, we'll discuss each of these foundational blocks through the lens of the authors' experiences in building such a collective aesthetic within the Supercontinent ensemble.

1. THE COLLECTIVE

1.1 Introducing SuperContinent

SuperContinent is a global audiovisual live coding ensemble that comes together for rehearsals and performances using the Estuary web-based platform (Ogborn et al. 2017). In their practice, the collective uses sounds gathered and designed by the ensemble members through the multiple coding languages available on Estuary, primarily MiniTidal, Punctual, and CineCer0.

Established under the "Platforms and practices for networked, language-neutral live coding", SuperContinent was formed to celebrate diversity, inclusivity, collectivity, respectful creation, and global distribution. Members have a geographic location at least 500 km from each other and the ensemble includes performers in India, Japan, UK, Portugal, Canada, South Africa, and Colombia.

Beyond existing across a wide range of timezones, SuperContinent strives to merge diverse artistic approaches through the collective design of strategic improvisatory stimulants and a generous collective sharing of sounds, techniques, resources, and tools—both synchronously and asynchronously. The ensemble has developed its identity through three years of weekly rehearsals, and performances at events such as NIME, ICLC, Network Music Festival, Half Stack Conference, and Montreal Connect.

1.2 The Ensemble's Objectives

The ensemble's main objective has always been to develop a group identity by negotiating shared live coding practices online through the Estuary platform. Estuary is "a browser-based collaborative live coding system" which aims to "explore the [...] potentials of projectional editing for live coding" (Ogborn et al. 2017).

As already recognized by the creators of the platform, the potential for using the plurality of projections through live coding can be greatly enhanced by using a shared browser interface. This also eliminates potential issues related to software installation and compatibility issues.

In the context of SuperContinent, the interface becomes analogous to a studio or a rehearsal room i.e, a place where musicians or artists meet to practice their art together. Following this comparison, different coding languages could be interpreted as different instruments (which sometimes result in different media such as audio versus visual) played or manipulated by members. As such, one of the objectives of the ensemble is to use the potential of telematics to recreate a collective dynamic similar in its experience to the one of artists meeting, rehearsing, creating, and performing in person.

2. NAVIGATING MULTIPLE LAYERS OF UNPREDICTABILITY

Live coding in its essence is rooted in unpredictability in the sense that the live coder doesn't always have the ability to predict the effect of their code (Rohrhuber et al. 2007). As we'll explore in detail in this section, in SuperContinent, the use of the Estuary interface results in layers of unpredictability stemming from multiple sources, each rooted in either human psychology or the use of technology.

2.1 Unpredictability in the Creative Process

While a musician's task is to primarily execute an idea, the live coder's task is about communicating an idea to the machine through code, therefore, delegating the execution part to the computer. In that sense, live coding could be compared to playing with another musician or visual artist with the live coder assuming the role of a "conductor", i.e. someone whose role is to communicate ideas to the artists rather than executing them.

Following this perspective, while it's possible for a conductor to work on their communication skills to communicate ideas as accurately as possible, there will always be a fragment of this idea that will be morphed or transformed due to delegating its execution to an exterior entity. This morphing of communication that can happen in the process is demonstrated, for example, in Magnusson's marimba piece where a marimba player is asked to interpret code-like notations, written on the fly (Magnusson and Eacott 2015). In live coding, while artists can develop their skills and their knowledge of the language to the point of having the ability to accurately communicate their ideas through code, there will always be a certain element of unpredictability introduced by the fact that live coders delegate the execution of that idea to the computer, and various aspects of error that can creep into the process (Knotts 2020).

This layer of unpredictability between human and machine accumulates in the context of a group of live coders improvising together. When two or more live coders collaborate, the scope between aesthetic idea and its formalization into media-producing code is multiplied. Code, compared to embodied means of executing creative ideas (e.g. through acoustic musical instruments) has a slower response time. The "beginning" and "end" of a specific execution are sometimes obscured due to the nature of the language, the system in use, the time it takes to type, and the cognitive overhead of translating a response into code form. This time delay adds complexity to the task of being 'in sync' with fellow group members.

During a rehearsal or performance, as the code develops in complexity and the sounds generated become denser, it gets harder to know which parts of the code are responsible for certain elements in the sound feedback loop. Thus, there is an interesting perspective in the act of listening created by the need for each individual to zoom in and out of their own sounds, sometimes focusing solely on the effects of their own code while editing it, and sometimes listening to the overall soundscape when developing ideas to fit in the general group aesthetic.

2.2 Unpredictability Introduced by Telematics

Oliveros describes three interdependent levels of organisation in telematic performance which are related in complex ways: the technical, the administrative, and the artistic (Borgo 2009). In SuperContinent, each of these levels brings with it an element of unpredictability for the performers.

A major difference between a remote live coding ensemble and a co-located group is, of course, the inability to view and respond to other members' body language (Hajdu 2017). In SuperContinent, the primary means of communication are sound and code, with an added layer of text messaging when using the Estuary's chat window or through post-rehearsal conversations in Discord.

During rehearsals, the chat window integrated into Estuary's layout is used for multiple purposes: voicing opinions about what members like or dislike during jams; check-in with others when technical issues arise, e.g. audio glitches caused by overloading the server; or deciding on a general aesthetic direction for the jam before starting to code.

While these modes of communication are useful in rehearsal, the inability to access body language introduces a question about real-time technical troubleshooting when performing in front of an audience.

In co-located performances, artists usually aim to obscure the elements mentioned above (opinions, resolution of issues, and artistic decisions) as much as possible in order to keep the performance experience intact for the audience. This is normally done by using each group member's skill to communicate effectively using solely body language. Since the use of telematics renders this impossible within SuperContinent, how much of these elements should be openly communicated through words to the public? How freely should members express themselves regarding technical issues?

Other telematic groups, such as OFFAL, lean towards full transparency for a number of reasons, including facilitating often arising technical issues, disrupting cultural norms of perfection in creative performance, and challenging hegemonic expectations around technical expertise (Knotts 2019). While SuperContinent also leans towards transparency and open communication with the audience, not everyone feels the same freedom to express themselves with words during a performance or rehearsal.

SuperContinent members do not believe in putting too much emphasis on perfection. However, in the heat of performance, time spent typing in the chat could sometimes be better spent resolving a technical issue or developing an idea, and communication through words is sometimes sacrificed to the purpose of tending to more urgent matters. However, critical issues such as server overload, which may be experienced unequally, do warrant group textual communication. This fact, coupled with the possibility of network issues, creates an additional layer of unpredictability for the ensemble to navigate. Each member will have a different way of adapting to these elements which affect the overall performance.

2.3 Human Unpredictability

Ensemble members each have a personal responsibility to attend rehearsals and performances as consistently as possible but everyone is subject to unforeseen circumstances or has to navigate a busy schedule. Rehearsals happen weekly on the same day and time but the group remains flexible and understanding of each individual's schedule and circumstances. This means the number and constellation of people attending each rehearsal and performance might differ, which affects the overall group aesthetic and dynamic.

This can, at times, be challenging, but also offers opportunities to develop the ensemble's collective identity. Working with a different subgroup of ensemble members almost every week allows individuals to step up in ways that are sometimes outside of their comfort zone by exploring different coding techniques or filling the sonic or visual space in a similar fashion to how one of the absent performers usually does. It is not only a question of how many people are present but also a matter of who is present that drives the way the ensemble navigates this layer of unpredictability. Witnessing the aesthetic direction different subgroups of members create has been a highly interesting and rewarding experience for the collective.

When working with a larger sub-group, individuals tend to write less code to leave space for others to participate. When working with a smaller subgroup—sometimes as small as two or three people—there is more space for each member to expand on their ideas. This unpredictability, dictated by the size of the subgroup present combined with each performer's specific aesthetic, has been a driving factor in the development of the group's collective identity, as well as being a source of motivation for each person to push the boundaries of their creative expression through the code.

3. AESTHETIC CHOICES BASED ON OUR RESPONSE TO UNPREDICTABILITY

Ultimately, there would be no point in navigating complex layers of unpredictability if it didn't serve a creative purpose. The main challenge in a remote collective live coding practice has been to transform the understanding of these layers into a clear identity i.e. a recognizable aesthetic presentable in a performance context defined and developed through consistent and conscious collective work. This implies certain aesthetic choices need to be made in light of the factors discussed in Section 2.

3.1 Group vs Individual Aesthetics

Maintaining an open mind and a non-judgmental attitude is a crucial part of allowing group members to be receptive to one another. This mindset helps each member to discover each other's personal aesthetic in a constructive manner by maximizing the use of each person's strengths, weaknesses, and preferences.

As noted previously, human unpredictability can affect the collective. This specific factor combined with a healthy mindset grounded in tolerance and flexibility gives each performer the sensitivity to adjust their personal contribution according to the subgroup of members present at a given time (e.g. according to whether the people present are more comfortable with abstract soundscapes or beat-based music).

The members of SuperContinent each have a specific background in the audio or visual spectrum—some having more experience manipulating visuals than sounds. More specifically, some members are more comfortable in the realm of abstraction and sound design while others have a clear preference in composing using defined musical elements; some members prefer finding methods of coding that distance the sonic space from clearly defined loops and patterns, while others enjoy crafting repetitive loops and patterns that gradually change over time. The non-judgmental attitude the collective has always strived to keep is a key factor in having the ability to respect each member's creative development and identity.

3.2 Collective Strategies

Reaching a collective identity as an ensemble is a constant work in progress and has never been straightforward. There was a point in the collective's development where the group was struggling to find cohesion and began exploring various methods that could help them become better at listening and following a cohesive direction rather than staying anchored in their individual comfort zones. During that period, it sometimes seemed like each person was unconsciously pushing towards their own aesthetic rather than focusing on creating a coherent result as a group.

Motivated by David Ogborn's reminders of the importance of striving for cohesion, the group came up with the idea of using collective strategies, which consist of abstract higher-level terms and descriptions defining various moods or methods to be applied during rehearsals or performances. The ensemble created a spreadsheet that includes various strategies, and consistently applied one of them in each of their rehearsals and performances over the course of four to six months. The goal of using these strategies was to focus on a general direction for improvisation without being overly restrictive of anyone's creative process or identity.

Name	Definition
abecedarian	Focusing on alphabet sounds (including Webdirt's "alphabet" sample folder). Building rhythms from alphabet-centered sounds. Using letter values in parameters (creating visual poetry).
euphoria	Broad major chord textures
frozen	Ambient, long, attempting to avoid any cyclical/loop

	feel
gravity	A general collective gesture to accelerate towards an abrupt stop (perhaps one person can be in charge of shifting tempo).

Table 1. Examples of collective strategies used by the SuperContinent ensemble.

Collective strategies have been an invaluable tool in the ensemble’s arsenal to focus on developing a group aesthetic. These strategies offered a template for group members to move out of their comfort zone by adapting their normal style or practice to the chosen strategy’s needs. When a strategy seems particularly foreign to a group member, there is always the option of stepping back and observing how other members develop the code, which is in itself a valuable learning experience.

At the time of writing, the group’s aesthetic identity and each person’s capacity to pay attention to their own contribution alongside staying attentive to the general direction of the collective has developed. Members now feel comfortable in letting their improvisations organically unravel without defining it beforehand with a specific strategy. Certain elements, such as tempo, are still discussed and agreed on prior to starting a live coding session, but more specific elements related to aesthetics are usually left open. This reflection is only an observation of the present reality and by no means implies the group will not revert back to using collective strategies at some point in the future.

3.3 Combining Approaches in a Performance Context

Before adopting the collective strategies tool, the ensemble’s performances tended to be inconsistent in quality and cohesion because it would usually take the group between 10 to 15 minutes to tune the general direction of the performance. Using a specific strategy ensures all members have a clearly defined focus when entering a performance and therefore helps the collective to get into a state of cohesive creative flow more quickly.

Another method used by the ensemble to achieve this level of cohesion during performances has been to sometimes agree on keeping the specific direction developed during the rehearsal prior to the performance. The collective might decide to simply retain some ideas explored in the latest rehearsal and use them as a foundation for the performance. This does not signify reusing the same code but it might involve taking previous ideas as inspiration or occupying the sonic or visual space in a similar way, i.e. riding the cohesive wave the ensemble has succeeded to catch during rehearsal. This approach can be useful in eliminating the confusion around “who does what” (e.g. if a certain member was particularly successful creating basslines in the latest rehearsal, they might choose to code basslines again for the performance).

4. BUILDING A COLLECTIVE IDENTITY THROUGH MULTIPLICITY OF EXPERIENCES

The accumulation of experiences both individually and as a group has an important part in developing the collective’s identity over time.

4.1 Multiplicity of Individual Experiences

The collective’s identity is greatly enhanced by the quality and quantity of experiences each individual brings to the table. Independently from the group, each member has a personal artistic motivation to keep learning and pushing the boundaries of their own creativity. In SuperContinent, each performer continues to improve their skills in using the languages present in the Estuary platform.

Independently from the perspective of the creative process, members are also active contributors to their respective local live coding communities as well as in the global TOPLAP community. The more each member is involved within these local and global communities, the more performing opportunities each one can bring to the group. This is a great asset in building the ensemble’s experience and it wouldn’t be

possible to have access to such a variety of opportunities if the collective wasn't composed of active independent performers and community leaders.

4.2 Multiplicity of Collective Experiences

The more performances the group accumulates, the better the ensemble becomes at dealing with the layers of unpredictability resulting from the action of performing. The group improves its ability to develop a cohesive performance within specific timeframes. Through performing, members have learned to address technical issues more efficiently.

Post-rehearsal communication is an important part of cementing the group's dynamic. By sharing their impressions, pitching new ideas, and bringing forward new resources after each session, members feed the collective's overall creativity and build long-lasting friendships by understanding and listening to each other on a human level. Members are able to build these friendships despite the geographical distance because the emotions generated by the experiences they share together through discussions, rehearsals, and performances are similar to the ones a co-located collective experiences.

Figure 1. A typical SuperContinent rehearsal. Photo © SuperContinent, 2021.

5. CONCLUSION

Building a collective aesthetic identity through a remote live coding practice is an ambitious objective and a constantly evolving process, but it also rewards the collective with a huge amount of valuable experiences, learning opportunities, human connections, and creative material fueling each individual's artistic development. The cohesive identity that SuperContinent has developed over the past year of experimentation with collective rehearsal processes suggests that the challenge of achieving a well-defined collective aesthetic through live coding using a web platform such as Estuary is not insurmountable.

Patience, trust in the creative process, consistency in the work while retaining an acute awareness of various layers of unpredictability, and respect towards each member's individual aesthetic are the fundamental building blocks that have allowed the ensemble to accumulate experiences leading to an ever-evolving collective identity. One could say that it is at the intersection of all these elements that a collective identity can be found, and most of the ensemble's work resides in a constant practice of finding and maintaining this delicate but beautiful equilibrium.

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